

1 **Fbxo32 functions in homeostatic cellular control through a specific redox sensor, Nmral2.**

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7 We explored a role for Fbxo32 as an influencer of chronic human disease pathology. We identified
8 Fbxo32 as a candidate for disease risk resulting from homeostasis loss prior to emergence of clinical
9 disease based on its presence in disease causal transcriptome datasets. A function for Fbxo32 in
10 homeostasis would support an essential role for loss of homeostasis and associated cellular degeneration
11 in emergence of the clinical disease phenotype ('threshold'). Fbxo32 could control elements of the
12 secretory pathway, which played a dominant role in cellular homeostasis: *Vti1b*, *Vps33b*, *Ap2b1* and *Pomt*
13 were cellular components of the secretory pathway most significantly affected by Fbxo32 function which
14 included more specialized secretory pathway components *Hycc2*, *Fkbp9* and *Pex19*. Fbxo32 obviously
15 affected iron homeostasis through *Cisd2*. We describe activation of a ubiquitin system based homeostasis
16 pathway controlled by Fbxo32 involving a separate homeostasis sensor, *Ufm1*. Fbxo32 functioned in
17 homeostatic cellular control through utilization of a specific redox sensor, *Nmral2*. We identify *Rad23b* as
18 a genomic correlate of cellular instability.

19 Citations

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